

WKB Versus Classical Density Approach to High Energy Level Entropy for an Oscillator Part 2

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In Part I, we considered the n dependence of Shannon's entropy for $n \rightarrow$ infinite using WKB and density $= C/|v(x)|$ ($v(x)=$ velocity) approaches. Here we generalized to a potential of the form x power $(2k)$. We argue that $S_n = 1/(1+k) \ln(n)$ to leading order using only scaling arguments. The classical turning points are $\pm x_n$ where: $x_n = \{ B(k) (n+.5) \}^{1/(1+k)}$ from (2).

No integrals need to be explicitly computed. Our main idea is that if $W(x, x_n)$, then the normalization condition: $1 = \int dx W^*(x, x_n)W(x, x_n) = 1 = x_n \int dx/x_n W^*(x, x_n)W(x, x_n)$. x_n is measured using a ruler and the result cannot depend on which ruler is used (i.e. different gradations). This means that $W^*(x, x_n)W(x, x_n) = 1/x_n$. Applying this to Shannon's entropy means that one has $S = \ln(x_n)$ to leading order or the result of (2). This result holds for both the classical density and WKB approaches.

General Idea

Consider $V(x) = x$ power $(2k)$ with classical turning points $\pm x_n$ given by a quantum mechanical result:

$$x_n = \{ F(k) (n+.5) \}^{1/(1+k)} \text{ where } F(k) \text{ is a function given in (2). } \quad ((1))$$

((1)) is taken from (2).

The main argument of this note is that the normalization condition cannot depend on which ruler one uses (i.e. on specific ruler gradations).

$$1 = \int_{-x_n, x_n} dx W^*(x, x_n)W(x, x_n) = 1 = x_n \int_{-1, 1} dx/x_n W^*W \quad ((2))$$

This, we argue, means that:

$$W^*(x, x_n)W(x, x_n) = G(k)/x_n \quad ((3)) \quad G \text{ is some function.}$$

This is the key idea of this note. We first apply it to the classical density approach for which the integral involved is simple.

This allows one to solve for Shannon's entropy without performing any integrals directly i.e.

$$S = - x_n \int_{-1, 1} dx/x_n W^*W \ln(W^*W) \rightarrow n \text{ dependence} = -\ln(1/x_n)$$

The x^n from $dx \rightarrow dx/x^n$ cancels with W^*W going as $1/x^n$, while a $1/x^n$ still remains in $\ln\{\}$.

Thus, S goes as $\ln(x^n) = 1/(1+k) \ln(n)$ ((3b))

This is the main result of the note.

Classical Density Approach

The classical spatial density is given by: $d(x,t) = C/|v(x)|$

Where for $m=1$ $v(x) = \sqrt{x^n \text{ power } 2k - x \text{ power } 2k}$ ((4))

This may be used to evaluate Shannon's entropy, but first C must be determined.

$1 = C x^n \int_{(-1,1)} dx/x^n \cdot 1/\{x^n \text{ power } k\} \cdot 1/\sqrt{1-y \text{ power } 2k}$ where $y = x/x^n$ ((5))

Thus, C goes as $x^n \text{ power } (k-1)$ ((6))

For Shannon's entropy: $S = - \int_{(-1,1)} dx/x^n \cdot x^n C \cdot 1/\{x^n \text{ power } k\} g(y) \ln\{C \cdot 1/\{x^n \text{ power } k\} g(y)\}$

One has for the n dependence of S :

S (n dependence) $\ln(1/x^n)$ ((7))

This is the desired result which yields: S (n dependence) $= -\ln(1/x^n) = 1/(1+k) \ln(n)$ ((8))

WKB Approach

Our argument in the first section holds for any wavefunction in general and so should apply to the WKB wavefunction given by:

$W(x,x^n) = \cos(\phi(x) - \pi/4) / \sqrt{f(x)}$ where

$f(x) = \sqrt{x^n \text{ power } 2k - x \text{ power } 2k}$ and $\phi(x) = \int (x,x^n) f(t) dt$ ((9))

Thus, one does not have to perform any integrals whatever and arrive at the result:

S n dependence $= 1/(1+k) \ln(n)$ ((9))

Conclusion

In conclusion, we use scaling ideas to argue that for a bound state with turning points $(-x_n, x_n)$, $W^*(x, x_n)W(x, x_n)$ goes as $1/x_n$ as the normalization integral does not depend on the ruler used.

Using this result in Shannon's entropy yields S goes as $1/(1+k) \ln(n)$ for $V(x) = x^k$.

This holds for any wavefunction or classical density. We consider two examples above.

References

1. Majernick, V. and Optharny, T. Entropic Uncertainty Relations for the Quantum Oscillator Article in Journal of Physics A Mathematical and General · January 1999 DOI: 10.1088/0305-4470/29/9/029 https://www.researchgate.net/publication/231048623_Entropic_uncertainty_relations_for_a_quantum_oscillator
2. Dehesa, J. et al. Quantum Information Entropies For Highly Excited States of Single Particle Systems with Power Type Potentials Article in Physical review A, Atomic, molecular, and optical physics · December 2002 DOI: 10.1103/PhysRevA.66.062109 This article was obtained from Semantic Scholar